

TEACHERS' DISCIPLINED BEHAVIOUR AND CODE OF ETHICS: IMPLICATIONS FOR THE FUTURE OF EDUCATION IN NIGERIA

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Abstract: *This paper examines discipline and code of ethics in the teaching profession. A critical evaluation of the disciplined behaviours of teachers in Nigeria through historical and philosophical lens connecting to the national code of ethics and the broader future of education in Nigeria. By examining the evolution of teacher education, cultural expectations, and ethical frameworks, it explores the moral imperatives required for transformative education. The paper argues that a reconceptualization of ethical discipline is essential for restoring dignity in the teaching profession and advancing educational outcomes in Nigeria. Many unethical behaviors in the teaching profession such as aiding and abetting examination malpractice by teachers; sexual misconduct; teacher absenteeism; corruption and financial misconduct; physical and emotional abuse of students; and negligence of duty/lack of commitment were explored. And these unethical behaviors have many negative implications and consequences for teachers, students, the teaching profession, and the society at large. It concludes that ethics is a crucial element in the teaching profession and is essential to teachers' professional conduct because virtuous acts such as honesty, integrity, fairness to mention a few, promote societal progress and welfare, while vicious acts such as dishonesty, injustice, and examination malpractice debase the nation's education system. Based on the foregoing, the paper recommends that there should be continuous professional development of teachers by the government; that there should be regular training of teachers on ethics, classroom management, and child's psychology; that there should be enforcement of TRCN code of ethics to ensure compliance; that erring teachers should be punished to serve as deterrent for others; that government should increase funding and infrastructure development to teacher training institutions to help them cope with their work environment; moral education should be introduced and made compulsory at all levels of our educational system; and examination malpractice, and other forms of social vices should be eradicated or controlled by enforceable and effective laws.*

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Introduction

Education is the process of human development that aims at equipping the learner with intellectual and moral values for his own development and for his contribution to the society in which he lives. Education in any society serves as a mirror and a mold; it reflects cultural values and shapes future generations. In Nigeria, the role of the teacher is not merely to instruct, but to model the ethical and disciplined conduct expected of a morally upright society. Nigeria has a philosophy of education, that is anchored on the development of an individual into a sound and effective citizen and his integration into the community and the provision of equal educational opportunities to all citizens, from the primary, secondary and tertiary levels inside and outside the formal school system irrespective of gender, ethnicity, religion, socio-economic status or any other real or imagined barriers (FME, 2020).

According to the National Policy on Education document, education in Nigeria aims at the inculcation of national consciousness and unity, the inculcation of the right type of values and attitudes for the survival of the individual and the society, the training of the mind in the understanding of the world around; and the development of appropriate mental, physical, social abilities and competencies for the survival of the individual and society (FME, 2020). Teachers are the life blood of a nation's education system. Their qualification, training, commitment, and experience are important

issues in the education system. In Nigeria, the operations of teachers are guided by teachers' service manual popularly referred to as teachers' code of ethics. Nwosu (2017) in his reflections on this service manual reiterated that it provided the ethical dispositions of the Nigerian teachers and adduced the critical issues posed in the service manual as follows:

- a. What are enduring human values that must be inculcated in the school system by teachers?
- b. How can teachers determine knowledge that enhances ethical standards in the learner?
- c. What is the rationale for emphasizing probity, accountability, and discipline as parameters for assessing human conduct?
- d. How can the school system be built on realistic moral values as a precondition for enhancing ethical standards in the society?

However, increasing concerns over teacher misconduct, low motivation, and erosion of professional standards call for a critical reassessment of teacher behaviour. The Nigerian education system is facing critical challenges resulting from indiscipline and poor teacher conduct that could question its existence. Hurd in Okere (2016) believes that the Nigerian education system is merely frog-leaping over inconsistencies. He opined that incessant teachers' strike actions, poor completion of curriculum materials, and the lack of disciplined efforts and ethical practices needed to attain a

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good education system are running counter to an effective and efficient system of education. The educational foundation of Nigeria tends to have been eroded by a rising tide of mediocrity to the extent of threatening the future of the nation and its people. Wokocha 2017; in his survey of student's achievement asserted that within the context of the modern scientific revolution, we are raising a new generation of Nigerians that are scientifically and technologically illiterate. He believes that educational programmes are inadequately funded, infrastructural and instructional facilities are in short supply while teachers embark on incessant strikes leading to poor completion of curriculum materials and low-quality graduates. These setbacks notwithstanding, the fervor of the quest for disciplined orientation and ethically-minded teachers has not diminished. Teachers' ethical code of conduct has remained the necessary tool for mobilizing the learners for national development and for addressing the challenges of the Nigerian education system.

The researchers have carried out literature review from studies on professional ethics. These include: dealing with students, treating co-workers, treating parents and the community, and performing activities and their related performance (Kafi & Motalliebzabeh, 2018). A research that was conducted on evaluation of professional ethics of employees' dispute resolution councils concluded that there is a significant relationship between professional ethics of employees and business identity variables, and individual variables such as education and training, Sadeghi; 2020. Researchers in a study entitled improving the

professional ethics of teachers in the educational system, concluded that the observance of educational ethics guarantees the health of the teaching-learning process in education and increases teachers' commitment to respond to students' needs. It is the task of this paper to demonstrate that maintaining teachers' disciplinary behaviour and the professional code of ethics is necessary for both immediate educational reforms and long-term improvements in teaching practice. The findings of this study would enable teachers to put up the behavioural and attitudinal changes necessary for revitalizing the nation's educational process. This is implicit for a proper understanding and commitment to the teachers' code of ethics.

Conceptual Clarifications

The concepts of teaching, discipline, and professional code of ethics are clarified for purposes of discussing and analyzing the task of the teaching profession.

Concept of Teaching

Teaching from the philosophical perspective recognizes the teacher as a significant order in guiding students learning and in providing an enriched educational environment that exposes the learner to a variety of learning experiences, minimizing verbal communication and giving leading questions; proving assistance when needed and helping the learners to organize information, encourage discussions and concept formation (Bebefiafai, 2015). The ethical disposition of the teacher is imperative for the broadening of social order, for a more rational handling of practical problems of human society, improvement of the surroundings of man, and the moral welfare of all. The teaching profession

presents three essential elements in a nation's education system. These are: the teachers, the learners and the instructional process. Teachers are the life-blood of any educational system for the schools cannot function effectively without them. Their qualification, experience, and training are vital to the nation's education system. Teachers are the organs through which pupils are brought into effective connection with the learning materials.

Concept of Teachers Disciplined Behaviour

Disciplinary measures form the fabrics on which modern societies thrive. This observation is in line with Bernard cited in Okere, (2018) who noted that: no society had been able to live without laws and regulations, and apparently the more complex the society, the greater is the need for detailed description of behaviours which are permitted and those which are proscribed.

From the various uses of discipline, Okere (2018) believes the following are worthy of mention:

- a. The orderly conduct and action which result from training; a trained condition;
- b. Instruction aimed at making pupils form proper conduct and action, acquire mental and moral training;
- c. A way of control, a way of life, the practice of human attitude of self-respect, respect for others, good behaviour, honesty, compliance to law and order, industriousness at work to mention a few. (Okere, 2018).

Concept of Teachers' Professional Code of Ethics

Professional ethics is a collection of values, standards and norms that each individual considered a professional should possess Iroegbu and Uyanga, in Okere, 2018. The main objective of the professional code of conduct of teachers is to rework the behaviour of the members within the teaching profession, preserve public interest, protect the profession, and discipline the members. Ethical issues are multifaceted. They cut across individuals, groups, organizations, national as well as psychological, sociological, economic and cultural variables. Ethics can be classified into professional, work, business, social to mention but a few. According to Okere 2018; ethics can be divided into three sections namely; descriptive ethics, normative ethics and applied ethics.

Descriptive ethics describes and introduces the ethics of individuals, groups, and societies. Normative ethics deals with what is the proper conduct of an individual or agent and applied ethics considers specific and important theoretical issues of environment. Professional ethics refers specifically to ethical issues of members of a professional body. Examples can include: the teaching profession, the medical, engineering; or any other professional groups or organization. Teachers are members of the teaching profession in Nigeria. The teaching profession is guided by certain principles, rules of conduct and behaviour which specify the discipline and behaviour expected of any person under the teaching profession. These behaviour patterns and conduct help to guide the actions of teachers in the performance of their duties. They equally, provide the parameters for measuring

the relations between teachers and students, parents, community, the society and the government. These principles also determine the responsibilities and roles expected of each member of the profession as well as the duties and roles of the employees and employers alike without which the profession would fail to realize its set goals and objectives.

Professional ethics can be approached using two perspectives; the traditional and the strategic management approach. According to Nwosu 2017; traditional professional ethics deals with ethics of the work-place or occupation. In other words, it is the expression of the principles, rules and ethical issues that bind each person to his profession according to the requirements of his job. They are the standards of human behaviour and conduct expected of individuals and groups in a profession based on ethical and moral principles. The strategic approach to professional ethics deals with the responsibility of the professional organization with a systemic approach. This relates to the moral responsibilities of people working in a particular job or profession and also, the moral responsibilities of the institution or professional organization under which people are working. That is to say, this approach considers the behaviour and attitude towards employees within the organization and even with the larger society.

Theoretical framework

The classical philosophers such as Socrates, Plato and Aristotle have emphasized the role of ethics and morality in education. Plato gave a highlight of the purpose of education when he noted that education aims at the nourishment

and upliftment of the spiritual dimension of human beings above the perfect and unchanging ideal world of reality. He emphasized that education should be concerned with training people to perform their respective duties in the society based on the principle of justice, which he regarded was the supreme goal of education. To achieve justice, Plato's ideal state recommended two major changes in the character of the state thus; the destruction of selfishness and the institution of communalistic life style and; the elimination of ignorance to ensure that the governance of the state is committed to those who proved themselves to possess the necessary knowledge and insight.

The Nigerian educational process has inherent moral nature. Education as a process of human development means a concern for the interest or welfare of persons other than the agent. As a societal institution, its purpose is to equip the future membership of the society to participate actively in the development of the society. In order to perform this role, education must distill a sense of responsibility, creativity, integrity, broad-mindedness and critical thinking among the learners. Arikpo in Nwosu (2017) believes that moral education is a deliberate and systematic effort to transmit...attitudes, beliefs and moral codes of a social group to learners for their moral upliftment. Mezieobi 2019; believes that moral education is an aspect of formal education through which teaching and learning process in educational institutions can inculcate acceptable behaviour, attitudes, habits of life, modes of conduct and their unacceptable or bad alternatives are exposed to learners who are ultimately guided to distinguish or discriminate

between rights and wrongs to enable them make informed and right decisions.

According to the Federal Ministry of Education (FME, 2020) in the National Policy on Education, the following sets of beliefs are stated: education is a tool for individual and societal development; functional education promotes progressive and united nation and education must be relevant, practical and comprehensive. Teachers are responsible for achieving the above objectives in the learners. Teaching results in learning and through learning, the educated person is produced. Teachers are the organs through which pupils are brought into effective communication with the learning materials. Teachers should play the roles of main communicators of knowledge and skills and the enforcer of rules of conduct.

History of Teacher Education in Nigeria

From the colonial period, through the independence and post-independence period, teachers have occupied a pre-eminent position. During the colonial period, most teachers received informal instruction in the homes of reverend fathers and pastor in charge of the various Christian denominations. Candidates were chosen for the promise they showed as leaders, for their intelligence and the zeal with which they embraced the word of God. As they were teacher-catechists the formation of good morals and abilities to preach the gospel were emphasized.

According to Alabekee (2017) the 1925 educational memorandum provided for religious training and moral instruction as fundamental to the development of a sound education based on a satisfactory cadre of

teachers and teacher training institutions. He also, asserted that there was a system of visiting teachers to ensure inspiration and encouragement.

The Phelps-Stokes commission of 1922 made some concrete recommendations for the teaching profession, which stated that:

1. The educational needs of the masses for the training of teacher and for the preparation of professional men should be clearly distinguished.
2. The Government should provide for the temporary employment of teachers of lower qualification on condition that adequate supervision could be supplied and facilities developed for the increased supply of better prepared teachers.

This commission also advocated for registration of teachers for approved university degree or diploma and any recognized teachers' certificate or other qualification considered adequate. Teacher education was equally emphasized in the independence period of the 1960 and above. Due to low output of teachers and poor quality of the teachers produced, there was the establishment of Teachers Grade II Training institutions, the upgrading of Teachers Grade I programme to Nigerian Certificate in Education (NCE) awarding institutions. Later with the Nigeria independence many universities were opened. They offered degree programmes of Bachelor of Arts (B.A.), Bachelor of Science (B.Sc.), Bachelor of Education (B.Ed.), in their faculties of Education.

The National Teacher Education Policy (2009) stipulates among others, the Vision, Goals, and

Objectives of Teacher Education in Nigeria. The vision of teacher education in Nigeria is to:

Produce quality, highly skilled, knowledgeable, and creative teachers based on explicit performance standards through pre-service, and in-service programmes who are able to raise a generation of students who can compete globally. The goal of teacher education according to the policy document is to ensure that teachers are trained and recruited to teach world class standards and to continue to develop their competencies in their entire career.

Specific objectives of teacher education include:

- i. To create adequate incentives to attract competent people into the teaching profession;
- ii. To ensure rigorous admission and graduation requirements and apply them consistently;
- iii. To ensure that teacher education institutions are well equipped both in human and material resources;
- iv. To ensure that teachers have sufficient mastery of content and varied methods of teaching that are subject-specific, including teachers for Special Needs Learners;
- v. To ensure structured, effective and supportive supervision of teaching practice and induction as well as certification and licensing;

- vi. To produce sufficiently trained teacher educators capable of imparting and modeling desired knowledge, skills and attitudes;
- vii. To motivate teachers and provide opportunity for their continuing professional development, retention, advancement and improvement in their chosen career; and
- viii. To ensure that teachers constantly upgrade their skills in order to remain competent and relevant.

The teaching profession has a corpus of knowledge that enables teachers to render essential services to the society. Teaching is more than doing and the job of the teacher is always concerned with developing human beings at their most impressionable stage. Children differ in intelligence, aptitude, interests and temperaments. The teacher should understand the human developmental process and the variabilities of each child in order to take the child to the next level. He is to transmit the accumulated knowledge of the past and interpret it with reference to the present; and be able to take this knowledge of the present into the future. As pointed out by Dewey in Okere (2022) the teacher must be able to inhabit both the world of the learner and of the adult society in order to establish a “continuum” between them. Thus, he should understand major trends in contemporary civilization and prepare the students to meet adequately the problems they may encounter at their mature period.

As a profession, there is a strong organization that is generally recognized as being able to speak for all members within the profession.

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This organization emphasizes ideals of service above personal gains. As a profession that is obligated to cultivate a responsible, disciplined, and useful citizenry for individual and societal contribution, teacher's impact is vital to the socio-economic, political and cultural emancipation of the Nigerian society.

The Nigerian education system expects the teacher to inculcate valuable knowledge, skills and expertise into the Nigerian child. Teachers need to develop sound educational values towards life generally. This translates to instruction in the entire realm of values such as physical, emotional, intellectual, imaginative, democratic, scientific, social, moral and spiritual for any individual (Okere, 2018). That is why teachers are responsible for inculcating worthwhile education that could translate to individual and societal development; and that education should be functional, relevant, practical and comprehensive. It should also inculcate the right type of values, and attitudes for individual and societal survival. Such values and attitudes encompass respect for each other, responsibility, tolerance and the intellectual resources to make informed and responsible judgement about difficult matters of moral importance.

What are Teachers' Disciplined Behaviour and Professional Code of Ethics?

Discipline is an important aspect of the teaching and learning process. From etymological perspective, discipline is derived from two Latin words, *discipulus* meaning a learner, a scholar, a follower or a disciple, and *disciplina* meaning instruction, intuition, teaching in the wider

sense (Okeke & Amirinze in Okere, 2018). Arising from the above perspectives, discipline relates to instruction that is, teaching and learning process. Given the phenomenal growth in the use of the word, discipline can refer to the process of training, or developing a person by instruction and exercise especially in self-control. A disciplined teacher is therefore, one who engages in self-control to achieve a goal or to maintain a certain standard of conduct; the ability to train oneself to do things that should be done and to resist things that should be avoided. In the teaching and learning process, teachers' disciplined behaviour could be demonstrated in teacher's knowledge and mastery of his subject matter, his commitment to service, his ability to build positive relationships with students, use positive reinforcement techniques and implement fair and consistent consequences for misbehaviour.

Discipline is a mode of life in accordance with laid down rules of the society to which all members must conform, and the violation of which are questionable and also disciplined. Discipline refers to a systematic instruction given to a disciple, a student. To discipline means to instruct a person to follow a particular code of conduct.

In the school system, teachers discipline constitutes a significant order for modeling character and of teaching self-control and acceptable behaviour. Effective school discipline strategies seek to encourage responsible behaviour and to provide all students with a satisfying school experience as well as to discourage misconduct. Discipline helps to develop the attitudes, habits, ideals which are

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conducive to the well-being of oneself, his fellows and society as a whole. It gives the school the opportunity to reconstruct human behaviour in line with a conscious pursuit of common goals in accordance with individual capabilities that could be consistent with life in a democratic society, and discipline becomes co-extensive with the whole of school life.

The role and importance of disciplined behaviour/ethics in teacher effectiveness cannot be over-emphasized. Two broad principles which could be used to appraise the ethical behaviour of teachers are the principle of benefit-maximization and the principle of equal respect. The principle of benefit maximization holds that the best decision is the one that results in the greatest benefit for most people. In philosophical parlance, it is known as utilitarianism and requires that teachers identify the particular benefits they wish to maximize in the learners, identify a suitable population for maximization, specify what is to count as maximization and fully understand the consequences of their actions. The second principle is the principle of equal respect. This principle demands that teacher's respect the equal worth of all people. This would require treating people as ends rather than means; to regard human-beings as free and rational; and to accept that they are entitled to the same basic rights as others. (Strike in Okere, 2024).

The rationale for discipline and professional code of conduct is for the broadening of social order and for a more rational handling of practical problems of human society in order to improve the surrounding of man and foster the moral welfare of all. Education aims at the

nourishment and the upliftment of the intellectual, moral and spiritual dimension of human beings. It trains humans to perform their duties in the society based on moral principles of justice, fairness, and freedom. In Nigeria, education equips the individual with knowledge, skills and competences. The ennobling roles of education in society include: responsibility, creativity, integrity, broad mindedness and critical thinking. These broad goals of education can only be achieved through discipline and adherence to professional code of ethics.

What is the Scope/Content of Discipline and Code of Conduct among Teachers?

Discipline in education encompasses a lot of issues including the teachers, learners, the curriculum and the evaluation of learning outcomes. An educated person is a disciplined person; one with moral values (Emeam, 2021). Discipline is a condition of being mature in thought, in behaviour, and in emotional expression. A disciplined person is a right-thinking person, one that considers the pros and cons of an action and tries to follow the principle of the golden mean between two extremes. Within the framework of the National policy on education (FME, 2020) the overall philosophy of Nigeria is couched on; the development of the individual into a morally sound, patriotic and effective citizens; total integration of the individual into the immediate community, the Nigerian society and the world as a global citizen and, the provision of equal access to qualitative education opportunities for all citizens at all levels of national education within and outside the formal school system.

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The scope of the professional standards for Nigerian Teachers can be classified under four themes. These include: professional knowledge; professional skills; professional values, attitude and conduct; and professional membership obligations.

Ethics is a branch of philosophy that is concerned with human conduct more specifically, the behaviour of individuals in society. Following ethical standards, individuals act in a responsible and accountable manner, promote trust, respect, and fairness. Ethics should be prioritized in this fast-changing world because it promotes trust and credibility which is the foundation of successful relationship and paves the way for building long-term partnership; fostering reliable, honest, and dependable interpersonal relationship. It also, promotes respect and fairness. Following the deontological theory, ethics is concern itself with the means and mindset of the person who is doing the action, specifically with the relationship between a person and his duties/obligations. Teachers' professional ethics involves regulatory mechanisms in teaching and learning process. These regulations have become necessary following the enormous responsibilities placed on teachers. These ethics are necessary for promoting professional excellence and self-satisfaction among the teachers and other stakeholders in education.

Furthermore, the code of ethics as provided in the teachers' service manual are guidelines to enable the teacher navigate through his jobs in line with the ideals and values system of Nigeria and in recognition of the worth and dignity of human beings based on moral principles of

justice, equality, fairness, freedom, etcetera. A strong teachers' code of ethics is crucial for the future of education in Nigeria. Ethical conduct ensures fair, impartial, and respectful interactions between teachers and students, fostering a positive learning environment. This code guides teachers in making ethical decisions, protecting students' rights, and maintaining professional standards, which are vital for building trust and confidence in the education system.

Orji in Okere (2016) avers that teachers' codes of ethics in Nigeria include:

- i. That the personal life of the teacher must be exemplary;
- ii. That contract should be fully executed both in spirit and in letter of law;
- iii. That the primary consideration of the teacher at any time should be the welfare of the pupils entrusted to his care;
- iv. That any teacher on leaving a position should leave enough records and information of the guidance of the successors;
- v. That relationship between co-workers should be characterized by the spirit of cooperation.

In addition to the above, full professionalism requires teachers to: be-liberally educated in terms of being exposed to wider knowledge, possess a body of specialized skills and knowledge related to an essential for the performance of the teacher's function and be able to make rational judgement and take appropriate action within the scope of the activities and be responsible for the consequences of their judgement and actions;

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actively participate with their colleagues in developing and enforcing standards fundamental to continuous improvements in the profession and abide by those standards in their own practice.

Role of Discipline/ Code of Ethics in Achieving Students' Academic Success

Education is necessary for the formation of good character, and development of the right type of values in students to be responsible and respectable citizens in our society. The National Policy on Education 2013; lays emphasis on the inculcation of moral and spiritual values in interpersonal and human relations and stressed that education should aim at total development of human being, morally, intellectually and in all aspects. A well-structured school environment with clearly defined discipline, and moral code of conduct can promote student success in the following ways: quality teachers, focused learning, safe and supportive environment, accountability and self-regulation., and co-operative students,

Quality Teachers. For quality education to be assured, best quality of teachers in character, knowledge, and professional competence must be recruited and retained, to ensure stability and progress of the education system. **Focused Learning.** Students can avoid distractions, and teachers can maximize instructional time which results in a safe and orderly classroom for learning. Time wastage is minimized on managing misbehaviour and this can improve student learning. Discipline teaches students, the value of punctuality, and code of ethics helps them develop self-discipline and organizational ability. As a result, procrastination is reduced

and attention is given to matters of urgent importance. **Safe and Supportive Environment.** A physically and emotionally learning environment devoid of bullying, harassment, and disrespect for each other promotes engagement and motivation to learn. A disciplined and ethically conscious learner will encourage better peer relationships, collaboration, and critical thinking skills which are vital for student academic success. **Accountability and Self-Regulation.** Strict adherence to discipline and code of conduct are vital ingredients for building accountability and self-regulation among students. This will help to instill character, reliability, maturity, and commitment. These qualities are necessary for promoting academic success, responsible students, and productive citizens. **Co-operative Students.** Quality education demands full co-operation and discipline of the students on daily school activities. Teachers should give clear and appropriate instruction and act as role models for students through their exemplary behaviour. This will make students to co-operate and collaborate with each other and with the teacher in carrying out instructions for purposes of academic success.

Quality Education Based Violations of Discipline/Professional Code of Ethics in Nigeria

It is important to note that the indicators of quality education as adduced above are still low in Nigeria. Amaele 2009; believes that none of the indicators of quality education and students' success has a fifty percent pass mark in Nigerian Public Schools. The teacher, government, and the general public share the blame for low

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quality education in Nigeria. There are also, systemic factors among which are: examination malpractice, corruption and financial misconduct, poor funding, and parental factor.

Examination malpractice constitutes a major hindrance to sound and quality education. Okere 2017; defines examination malpractice as any action done or committed which makes it impossible to use an examination in determining the level of competence of a candidate in absorbing, deducing and where appropriate, applying knowledge. He opined that forms of examination malpractice such as examination fraud, mass cheating in internal and external examinations to buying grades, can disrupt the school system and the consequences could result to lowering of examination standards, and its obvious disruption of the national education system.

Corruption and Financial Misconduct. Corruption is against the genuine purpose of any system. With corruption in education, quality will be far-fetched. The Nigerian educational sector is the largest of all the public sectors. The corruption in the larger society has reflected greatly on the education sector. These corrupt behaviours affect the students, teachers and parents, thereby shaking the foundations of quality education. Okurounmu, 2004; observes that corruption has become a game in the education system and all the stakeholders are involved. Teachers by training, should be role molders of characters of learners. But contemporary experience has shown that teachers now introduce their pupils to the culture of cheating, sexual harassment, lying,

and other forms of immorality and corrupt practices. (Okurounmu, 2004).

Poor Funding. Poor funding of educational infrastructure such as human and material resources, laboratory, technical and vocational facilities, conducive classroom and hostel facilities, have become major features of Nigerian schools. These are contrary to the indicators of quality education.

Parental Factor. Parents sometimes collaborate with the officials of the Ministry of Education and school authorities in corrupt practices to ensure that their wards/children are admitted into Unity Secondary Schools. Many coaching centres for JAMB preparation and Examination into higher institutions have sprang up, some of which specialize in procuring question papers in advance for students. These factors pose serious threat to Nigerian education.

Ways Teachers Can Achieve Discipline in Education

Education is concerned with human development and true development rests on man; the unfolding and realization of his creative potential in order to enable him to improve his material conditions of living through the use of resources available to him. Human beings need the right environment, orientation, and discipline. Discipline is the foundation of any realistic educative process. The Nigerian education landscape is characterized by high incidence of indiscipline which has in turn promoted the falling standards of education.

The Nigerian education system envisions that individuals should be equipped with useful knowledge, skills and competencies for survival

and for contributing towards societal development. This translates to developing appropriate democratic values, freedom, social justice, and self-reliant citizens (FRN, 2013). That is why the training of teachers to meet these expectations is challenging.

Nwosu (2017) believes that the present-day students no longer believe that examination success can be achieved by burning the midnight candle but bribery and offering sexual gratification to teachers. This makes discipline and high ethical standard imperative for revamping the education system. He adduced the underlisted as strategies that could stem the continuation of indiscipline in the school. They include among others: exhibition of disciplined behaviour on the part of the teacher as a pre-condition for inculcating discipline in the learners, school environment should be made wholesome by providing basic amenities, good behaviour should be rewarded and bad character discouraged, guidance and counselling services should be initiated and promoted in the school, emphasis should be placed on area of specialization so that a teacher should have a good mastery and command of his subject matter, the teacher should be a model of discipline and should contribute effectively to efficient functioning of the school.

Strategies for Teachers to Achieve Discipline/Code of Conduct in School

From the foregoing, the teacher can demonstrate discipline in his teaching profession through the following:

Setting clear expectations and consistency in implementing them.

Building positive relationships. Teachers should build positive teacher-students relationships, establish trust, respect, and open communication to encourage students to behave responsibly and engage meaningfully with the learning process. Teachers should provide constructive feedback to foster a sense of belonging, which encourages disciplined teaching and teacher education.

Effective classroom management strategies. Employ management techniques to foster discipline and promote productive learning environment. Such techniques include: the use of non-verbal cues, praise for positive behaviour reinforcement, and the use of behavioural interventions can help to reduce disruptions and deviance.

Modeling professionalism and behaviour: Teachers' professional conduct such as punctuality, lesson preparation, and ethical behaviour in terms of respect and recognition can give rise to a disciplined classroom environment.

Adapting to technology in education. Teachers who integrate technology in their classroom can support and challenge indiscipline in teaching. Advance in education. This depends largely on the qualifications and ability of the teaching staff in general and in the human pedagogical and technical qualities of the individual teachers.

The status of teachers should be commensurate with the needs of education as essential in the light of educational aims and objectives.

Teaching should be regarded as a profession; a form of public service which requires of teachers' expert knowledge and specialized skills, acquired and maintained through rigorous and

continuing study, calling for personal and social responsibility for the education and welfare of the pupils in their charge.

Code of ethics or of conduct should be established by the teachers' organizations since such codes greatly contribute to ensuring the prestige of the profession and the exercise of professional duties in accordance with agreed principles (UNESCO, 2023).

Enforcement of Teachers' Discipline and Professional Code of Ethics through Teachers Registration Council of Nigeria (TRCN) Guidelines

The TRCN Act No. 31 of 1993 (Now CAP T3 of the Laws of the Federation of Nigeria, 2004), the council is empowered to regulate and control the teaching profession at all levels of the education system. Central to this mandate is the code of professional conduct for teachers. This code outlines acceptable behaviours and disciplinary standards expected of registered teachers. It specifies teachers' responsibilities to include: commitment to the students, commitment to parents, commitment to the community, commitment to the employer, and commitment to the profession. The foregoing rules and regulations help to ensure that teaching results in guiding the learner to acquire saleable knowledge, skills and values of the Nigerian society for him to become socially responsible, economically efficient, and morally sound. It is believed that these principles would enable the child to live in harmony with other members of the society, and to live a happy and responsible life. The teacher is therefore, under obligation to the students to deal justly and impartially with

them irrespective of their physical, mental and emotional or any other real or imagined barriers; to recognize and respect individual differences among learners and seek to meet the individual learning needs; not to enter into any indecent relationship with the learners in his school; to make discreet use of all available information about the learners; and to help the learners develop and appreciate the array of privileges and benefits that are available to them.

Closely related to the foregoing is commitment to the parents. As stakeholders in the education of the learners, the teacher is under obligation to the parents to share the responsibility of improving the educational opportunity for all; to respect the basic desire of parents for the education of their children; to help and increase the child's confidence in his home and help to avoid any distractions on the achievement of these goals; to provide parents with information that will benefit their children and make careful and judicious use of information received from parents. This will help to ensure that parents are kept informed about the progress of their children in line with the purpose of the school. As mentioned earlier, Nwosu (2017) posited that Nigerian Teachers Service Manual not only specifies the moral code for teachers in the strive for professional excellence but also, establishes mechanisms for promoting teachers' personal integrity. Teachers therefore, are guided by societal value systems in transmitting valuable knowledge and skills to learners who in turn are expected to imbibe the values of accountability, probity and discipline in their school career. It is expected that the school system should reflect the norms, values, and morals for societal

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cohesion and stability. Furthermore, Nwosu believes that the teaching profession should be committed to the community by ensuring public trust in the teachers' conduct and in his interaction with the school and the community. The achievement of this goal requires teachers to adhere strictly to reasonable patterns of behaviour accepted by the community; discuss controversial issues in an objective manner as not to incite public or learner outrage; recognize and encourage community participation in the school programmes, fulfill their corporate social responsibility; and work to raise educational standards in order to strengthen the community's moral, spiritual, social and intellectual life.

In addition, the teaching profession should maintain a commensurate employer-employee relationship. This helps to ensure mutual respect, understanding and good work ethics. This will amount to the following behaviour: conduct of professional duties in line with established principles and policy; refraining from disclosing confidential and official information with unauthorized persons; adhere to the conditions of the contract or appointment until the contract is terminated formally by mutual consent or legally; and give sufficient notice of any change of status or position or services. The above responsibilities placed the teacher at varying levels of significance. He is not only a purveyor of knowledge, information and skills but also, a democratic and socializing agent. He helps school children to become useful, gain social and emotional competences and live democratic lives.

Consistent with the principles of utilitarian morality which involve us in doing certain actions and refraining from performing certain actions, the teaching profession presents a wide range of sanctions or punishments for unethical teachers' code of conduct that could attract punishment. According to Nwosu (2017) the infractions on ethical conduct that could attract punishment include but not limited to the following: conviction for felony or misconduct; unlawful carnal knowledge of pupils or students of the school; indecent dealing with a student or pupils; conduct prejudicial to the maintenance of good order or discipline in a school. He noted that the code of ethics further provides for dismissal from service if a teacher absents himself from duty without leave or similar penalty or penalty appropriate to the circumstance if a teacher indulges in frequent lateness to school after three warnings. He also believes that every case of absence without leave would attract no pay for the period of such absence. From the foregoing, there is need for enforcement of TRCN Act to ensure that teachers adhere strictly to professional code of conduct.

Enforcement Mechanisms to Strengthen the Achievement of Discipline/Professional Code of Ethics

From the foregoing, any breach of the ethical guidelines is considered professional misconduct and is liable to disciplinary action by TRCN. The Teachers' Registration Council of Nigeria (TRCN) enforces teachers professional conduct through the following: teachers' registration and licensing; Professional Disciplinary Committee (PDC); Sanctions and

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Penalties. The council is empowered to register and license qualified teachers, accredit, monitor and supervise the courses and programmes of teacher training institution in Nigeria to ensure that they meet national and international minimum standards. They also, organize internship schemes for fresh education graduates in order to equip them with the necessary professional practice.

Professional Disciplinary Committee. The teachers' disciplinary committee is a tribunal that is responsible for considering and determining any case referred to it by the Teachers Investigation Panel (TIP). It consists of the chairman of TRCN, and ten other members appointed by the council. According to Nwosu 2013; the committee has power to punish a teacher where: he is judged by the committee to be guilty of infamous conduct in any professional respect or, he is convicted by any court or committee in Nigeria or elsewhere having power to award imprisonment; the committee is satisfied that the name of any person has been fraudulently registered.

These value orientations put the teacher at such a position to not only perform his duties through teaching and instruction but also to mold the character of the school children in a manner that would produce citizens whose concept of morality will fully align with the Nigerian value systems and also ensure that the individual is qualified in learning and in character. Teachers' ethical conduct hinges on providing quality education to Nigerian citizens in line with the ideals and values system of Nigeria and in recognition of the worth and dignity of human beings based on the principles of justice, equality

and freedom. These provisions have implications for the future of education in Nigeria.

Implications for the Future of Education in Nigeria

Discipline and professional code of ethics have implications for the future of education in Nigeria. Disciplined behaviour and code of ethics for teachers are critical components in shaping the quality and outcomes of education in any society. In Nigeria, these principles have profound implications both positive and negative. The positive implications include:

Punctuality and Regular Attendance to Classes: Teachers should be regular to classes in order to inculcate the same principle of punctuality in the students. **Diligence in Lesson Planning and Delivery.** Teachers should be diligent in planning and in preparing their lessons. **Respect for Students, Parents and Colleagues.** The dignity and worth of students, parents, and colleagues should be respected by the teacher. **Professionalism in Interactions.** The interaction between the teacher and his colleagues should be mature, ethical and devoid of immoral and nasty conversations. **Maintenance of Classroom Decorum and Authority.** Teachers should also show sanity and decorum in handling the teaching and learning process and in the exercise of authority in classroom management. Teachers ethical conduct and discipline could positively impact the broader education system in Nigeria by building a holistic educational system and providing an interpersonal relationship between the teacher and the learner. Ethical education aims at injecting

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sanity and raising the levels of moral awareness of the learners. This would encourage the learners to imbibe and internalize the spirit of hardwork, honesty, integrity, and fairness in their dealings with the larger society. Nwosu (2017) believes that education is a moral issue and that an ethically and morally upright teacher would resist unwholesome acts and practices such as aiding and abetting examination malpractice, sexual harassment, to mention a few. **Guidance and Counselling.** Disciplined and ethically oriented teachers guide, train and mentor students. Through the training and mentoring process, the student could develop initiative, creativity, confidence and self-reliance. Educational policy makers, school administrators, and teacher unions should align teacher disciplinary practices with ethical and educational goals.

As a corollary, the negative implications include: decline in education quality; unethical conduct; loss of public trust; and increased drop-out rates. Decline in Education Quality. Indiscipline such as teachers' absenteeism, lateness to work, and poor lesson delivery negatively impart students' understanding and performance. Unethical conduct such as sexual harassment, favoritism, and bribery can erode students' values and trust in the system. Loss of Public Trust. Widespread unethical practices may lead to the public losing faith in teachers and the education system as a whole. Increased Drop-out Rates. Harsh or unethical treatment may push students out of school, especially vulnerable groups like girls, or students with disabilities.

Conclusion

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Nigeria has a robust and an ambitious system of education that is geared towards making the individual effective, efficient, and socially competent. Teachers discipline and professional competence are necessary for transmitting the right kind of knowledge, information, skills and competence to the learners and also, for providing professional guidance and mentorship to students so that they could develop in personal and social competence. Given the tradition and general world view of the citizenry, teachers are faced with the challenge of blending the old and the new morality. This would require acquiring the imaginative complexity and firm empathetic moral disposition that would enable them to positively influence the educational process. From this moral standpoint, the teacher is predisposed to produce citizens whose concept of morality will be in tandem with the Nigerian value systems and consequently, ensure that the learner is qualified both in learning and in character. Ethical regulations aim at ensuring that human beings live together harmoniously in society to enhance the living conditions of individuals and it is difficult to achieve purposeful development in our educational system without some form of discipline. This makes the teaching profession one with a plethora of knowledge, skills, attitudes, and code of conduct necessary for delivering on the job inside and outside the classroom environment. Teachers are knowledgeable people and are supposed to possess relevant subject-matter knowledge, and the pedagogical skills, as well as the ethical and moral standards to navigate their job. These measures help to ensure that teachers operate under guidelines, ensure conformity to

moral standards, and help to achieve national educational objectives.

However, experience has shown that there are common violations of teachers ethical codes such as examination malpractice, poor funding of human and material resources for education, sexual misconduct, corruption and financial misconduct, and physical and emotional abuse of students which often times constitute a clog in the wheel of achieving quality education and national development. These issues need to be properly addressed to ensure that the teaching profession is sound and alive to its responsibilities.

Teachers discipline and code of ethics is critical to a good education system. Effective teacher discipline seeks to encourage responsible behaviour and to provide all students with a satisfying school experience as well as to discourage misconduct. Teachers' discipline also helps to develop the attitudes, habits, ideals and code of conduct through the medium of the social life of the school which should be organized on a co-operative basis and inspired by highest ethical teaching of standard. Ethical codes for teachers enable them to deal justly and impartially with learners. Professional teacher training improves teachers' skills and performance. Adequate professional training helps teachers update their knowledge, and motivation in the form of better benefits and good working conditions foster dedication to duty and contribute to a positive work environment. This would help to ensure that teachers are professionally and morally committed, understandably more than any other professionals to the upliftment of the human

society, and therefore, professionalization of the teaching profession anchored on strong moral principles provides the solid foundation for the anticipated societal rejuvenation for the 21st century renaissance.

Recommendation

The following recommendations have been put forward:

- a. Continuous professional development of teachers by the government.
- b. Regular training of teachers on ethics, classroom management and child's psychology.
- c. Enforcement of TRCN code of ethics to ensure compliance.
- d. Punishment of erring teachers to serve as deterrent for others.
- e. Moral education should be introduced and made compulsory at all levels of our educational system; and its curriculum should include nine core values such as: honesty, right attitude to work, justice, discipline, citizens' rights, contentment, courage, national consciousness and right regard and concern for the interest of others; and
- f. Examination malpractice, cultism and indecent dressing among others can be eradicated or controlled by enforceable and effective laws, as well as, creating conducive learning environment and providing adequate human, material and financial resources.

References

Alabeke (2017) *Issues in historical foundations of Nigeria education systems*. Corporate Impressions.

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- Amaele, S. (2009). The child and the right to quality education: An approved of the Nigerian situation. *African Journal of Educational Studies (AJES)* 3(2) 23-41.
- Bebibiafiai, I. A, (2015). *Introduction to philosophy of education: Contemporary issues in the Nigerian educational system*. Café Publishers International Limited.
- Emeam, I. I (2021). *Philosophy of education. An introduction*. Career Publishers.
- Federal Ministry of Education, (2020). *National Policy on Education*. NERDC Press.
- Federal Republic of Nigeria (2013). *National Policy on Education*. NERDC press.
- Kafi, Z. & Motalliebzabeh, K. (2018). University instructors' teaching experience and their perception of professional ethics: Postulating a model. *International Journal of Instruction*, 11 (4): 257-259.
- Mezieobi, K. A. (2019). *Social studies in Nigeria: Teaching methods, instructional materials and resources*. Acadapeak Publishers.
- Nwosu, O. (2013). *The dynamics of Nigerian educational philosophy: Critical analysis and synthesis*. Osyora Nigeria Limited.
- Nwosu, O. (2017). *Ethics and the teaching profession: Correlation matrix and critical challenges* Labyrinths Publishers.
- Okere, J. E. (2017). *Philosophy of education: focusing higher institutions*. Uzopietro Publishing Company.
- Okere, J. E. (2016). *Philosophy of technology education in Nigeria: Past and Present*. Institute of European Studies, Belgrade, Serbia.
- Okere, J. E. (2018) *Philosophical foundations of education*. Finbach Company Limited.
- Okere, J. E. (2022). Equal education opportunity and self-reliance: The Nigerian Experience. *Nigerian Journal of Educational Philosophy (NJEP)*. 33 (1). 261-263.
- Okere, J. E. (2024). Gender equity and human development: Implications for the Nigerian tertiary education. *Nigerian Journal of Educational Philosophy (NJEP)*. 34 (1). 100-103.
- Okurounmu, F. (2004). *The anatomy of corruption in Nigeria*. Nigerian Tribune, July 15 p. 25.
- Sadeghi, E. (2020). *Evaluation of professional ethics of Tehran dispute resolution councils' staff*. 7th National Conference on New Research and Studies in Humanities, Management and Entrepreneurship of Iran, Tehran Iran.
- UNESCO, (2023). *Adverse consequences of social closures*
<https://enunesco.org/covid10/educationresponse/consequences>
- Wokocho, A.M. (2017). *Quality and universal basic education programme (A book of reading)* Osia International Publishers. Vol. 11. 60-62.